

THE PLACE OF FOLK GAMES IN HISTORY

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Abstract: *The article deals with the role of folk games in the past. Games play a significant role in educating the younger generation as they reflect the way of life, work, customs and traditions of the people. The valuable ideas of our ancestors on folk dances are also mentioned.*

Key words: *folk games, goat-kupkari, lapar, ulan and alla melodies.*

АННОТАЦИЯ: *В статье рассматривается роль народных игр в нашей истории. Игры играют важную роль в воспитании подрастающего поколения, поскольку отражают образ жизни, работу, обычаи и традиции людей. Упоминаются также бесценные игры наших предков и народных танцах.*

Ключевые слова: *народные игры, купкари, лапар, улан и алла мелодии.*

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada xalq o'yinlarining tariximizdagi o'rni ko'rib chiqiladi. O'yinlar xalqning turmush tarzi, mehnati, urf-odat hamda an'analari o'zida aks ettirgani uchun yosh avlod tarbiyasida muhim ahamiyat kasb etishi aytiladi.. Xalq o'yinlari haqidagi ajdodlarimizning bebaho fikrlari ham tilga olinadi.*

Kalitso'zlar: *xalq o'yinlari, ko'pkari, lapar, o'lan hamda alla kuyi*

Folk games have long been revered as an integral part of the cultural life of our ancestors. A lot of games possess very ancient roots and have served to enrich the spirituality of mankind, deepen his thinking and emotions over the centuries, reflect the lifestyle, hard work and achievement. Traditions and ceremonies, which reflect the unique sincerity of the Uzbek people, are a reflection of the beauty of ancient culture. Folk games bring a special joy, affect the mood, bring about physical, mental and moral development, make people strong, agile, resourceful, intelligent and courageous. Uzbek folk games are a unique genre of national independence, a device that dates back to ancient times. They featured national music (trumpets, drums and flute), which was a one-time celebration and become a part of folk art, reflecting the past and present culture and life of the Uzbek people. Uzbek folk dances were originated in ancient times. This was also

confirmed by archeological excavations and ethnographic materials by the ancient Roman historian Elian. It is said that games were very common in the Saks tribe and were a favorite custom of the people. The testimony showed that the boys of the Saks tribe had the right to marry the girls they had defeated in the game. The content of traditional Uzbek folk games are very rich and diverse, with a definite historical character and are especially popular on holidays weddings and celebrations. Most festivals include songs, performances of folklore and ethnographic groups, lapar, ulan, alla melodies and national folk games.

A game is also a national value that arises from physical competitions, contests, debates and performance requirements based on certain rules or pre-agreed conditions with different expressive powers. Games improve not only the mind and thinking, but also the role of exercises in human fitness as well. Even one can be the witness of some crucial advice of Ibn Sina, one of the most eminent Muslim physicians, in the Laws of Medicine which deals with the healing properties of the game, the role of wrestling and bodily exercises in physical education. Besides, other great people like Kaikovus, Umar Khayyom, Abulkosim Firdavsi, Beruni wrote about the profit and value of chess, backgammon, fencing, tyrannosaurus and horse riding in social life. The great Uzbek poet Alisher Navoi's works contain a lot of information about holidays, celebrations and weddings in which the organization, performance and conduct of the games are carefully discussed. Moreover, Mahmud Khoshgari's famous work "Devoni lug'otit turk" plays an essential role in the study of the history of national games namely more than 150 folk games are mentioned carefully. These include "dark" (castle in the dark), "bandol" (captivity), "pass-pass" (round game), "chavgon" (ball), "grass bandal" (stick game), javelin and other games, namely some of them are still fun activities for children and adults played especially on several national holidays. While casting a glance at the folk epic, "Alpomish" is considered an important source in the study of folk games which embodies some qualities like courage, fighting, bravery, perseverance, spiritual and physical perfection, based on games such as wrestling, horse-race, javelin, archery, fencing, sniper.

Besides regular types, there are also games according to seasons. For instance, "olbargak", "flower game" are played in Spring, whereas "fear", "snowstorm" are Winter games, "rain when it's raining", "storm when the wind blows", "hung up", "find the riddle", "say it fast", "who said it" pertain to Autumn.

Competitions, sports games and entertainment such as "Crowd race", "Girl chase", "Kurash", "Agdarish", "Kupkari" will be held during the festivals. From time immemorial, Uzbekistan has hosted festivals related to the labour process of

farmers- "Harvest Festival", "Melon Festival" in every region. Such ceremonies are mainly the result of the end of the harvest. An Uzbek folk games such as "Melon is ripe", "Pumpkin sign" are the samples among them. There are many ancient games around the Uzbek people, some of which are briefly described. "Capricorn game" ,the most complex and interesting game is known from X-XI centuries, and is played at major holidays and weddings. The most attractive part was that before the wedding a group of young horsemen gathered. The carcass of a slaughtered goat was the most essential thing that a lot of young men lifted the goat's body off the ground and gave it to those around it, trying to carry it to the finish line in May. Only young men who were quick, brave, strong-willed and did not stumble in difficult situations could take the kid to the finish line.

Another charming Uzbek national game was wrestling. Strong people were highly respected among the people, everybody around them looked at them with envy and praised them. The wrestlers, who wrestled for this purpose, were the guests of honor at public celebrations and conferences. A game of mutual struggle, a new kind of wrestling has long been a favorite pastime of the Uzbeks. The national wrestling is organized at every holiday and every public gathering. During the war, the two opposing sides lined up the strongest wrestlers in their armies. They fought with swords, bows and spears. When all the weapons were out of order, the wrestlers showed the strength with their hands, with a new fight. In this battle, the army that was on the side of the wrestler who defeated his opponent was considered the winner. In the newer generations of modern Uzbeks, wrestling was one of the traditional customs. Consequently, the current struggle has originated in very ancient times, the historical sources of the struggle for the result of showing strength, agility, installation, courage. Additional details of the struggle are given in the works of Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur as well. So wrestling has been a tradition of our people for three thousand years . Pahlavon Mahmud , a great poet and thinker of Khorezm who lived in 1247, is one of the promoters of Uzbek wrestling in the world. For more than 40 years, he was a wrestler who did not touch the ground in broad days, in Movaraunnahr, Khorasan, India, Iran and other countries.

In conclusion, folk games are a very important part of a people's heritage and culture. They preserve age-old traditions, deal with cooperation, interaction and independence that foster fundamental skills and determine person's accomplishments in education as well as in his interpersonal relationships.

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